

FASHION aLIVE

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	4.3
TITLE	Presentations/contents to be discussed in the roundtables
DUE DATE	Month 13
ACTUAL DATE OF DELIVERY TO EC	21 June 2023

GRANT NUMBER	101056307
PROJECT ACRONYM	Fashion Alive
DURATION	24 months
WEBSITE	https://fashion-alive.com/
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WORK PACKAGE	4
WORK PACKAGE LEADER	CREAMODITE
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DELIVERABLE VERSION NUMBER	0.3
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PU - Public

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Executive Summary

The following report contains the plan, agenda and contents which will be discussed during the Fashion Alive roundtables, which will take place on the first day of each partner's event in Madrid, Aversa and Guimaraes.

The objective of said roundtables is to disseminate project achievements during year 1 of the project, raise awareness about the project activities, and offer an introduction to the second day of each event in which the sustainable collections will be showcased in a performance runway event.

Introduction

Fashion Alive roundtables are an essential part of the events that the project partners will organize after the sustainable fashion collections are completed. They will help to achieve our objective of **developing and engaging audiences in sustainable fashion**, to promote the sustainable design methods developed by the partners and inspire others to incorporate, adapt and develop their own sustainable fashion design methods.

Stemming from this goal, the contents of said roundtables will cover the following aspects:

- **Project mission and achievements during Year 1:** partners will present a brief overview of what Fashion Alive has set out to accomplish in terms of developing and promoting sustainable fashion. Additionally, each partner will deliver a presentation on the sustainable design method they have developed.
- **Collaboration and debates on sustainable fashion:** Each partner will invite relevant local personalities to discuss hot topics on the sustainable design and development agenda.

The roundtables will be held live in local venues in Madrid, Guimaraes and Aversa, and made available via streaming to enable international participation. Afterwards, the footage will be edited and uploaded to the project website and YouTube channels.

The tone for the discussions will be relaxed, incorporating sufficient technical precision to make the understandable both to fashion professionals, amateurs, and the general public. Moreover, technical implementations will be planned to allow for the public's participation both during the live events and the streaming.

Agenda

Creamodite

The first roundtables will take place on May 18th, 2023, at Ateneo de Madrid, in the same location where the performance runway show will occur on the following day. It will also be live streamed through Creamodite's YouTube channel. After each demonstration, there will be a Q&A where the audience, both live and via streaming will be able to participate. They will be held in English and Spanish to engage the local and international audience.

Zero Waste Fashion Method Masterclass (Spanish, English subtitles on streaming)

Gisela Fortuna, lead investigator for Creamodite, will present a 30-minute overview of the Zero Waste Fashion Method. The focus will be on disseminating the results obtained, the applications, challenges, and opportunities that the method offers.

Sustainable Fashion Design and Production (Spanish, English subtitles on streaming)

Relevant Spanish personalities from leading sustainable fashion companies and brands will share their perspective on the implementation, advances, and challenges in sustainable fashion in Spain.

- Juan Carlos Mesa, founder of cult Spanish Fashion Brand Maison Mesa and creative director for Fashion Alive Madrid
- Sandra García Rodríguez, business development director for Pyratex, a Spanish textile company that pioneers in sustainable fabric production.
- Charo Izquierdo, renown Fashion, sustainability, and lifestyle consultant.

Fashion Alive Project (English)

One member from each organization will participate in this roundtable discussion, which will inform the public about project breakthroughs and discoveries during Year 1.

- Martina Gesell, project manager and member of Creamodite will present a brief overview of the project and moderate the debate.
- Roberto Liberti, lead investigator of Ucampania, will deliver a presentation on their research and achievements on Cultural Heritage and Sustainable Fashion
- Ana Cristina Broega, lead investigator of Uminho, will present Uminho's research and developments on Upcycling and Circular Fashion

This will be an opportunity for the partners to promote the project and engage the audience to participate in the upcoming events.

Uminho

The roundtables on Circular Fashion and Upcycling will be held in Universidade do Minho's Ázurem Campus Library on June 1st. It will also be livestreamed on Zoom; the video link will be shared in advance to enable audience participation online. The focus will be on raising awareness on post-consumer textile waste production and how to tackle this issue in the fashion and textile industries.

After each presentation, a Q&A will be held where the on-site and online audience will be able to participate. They will be held in Portuguese, Italian and Spanish to engage the local and international audience.

Fashion Alive Project (Spanish, Portuguese and Italian)

Participants:

- Gisela Fortuna (CREAMODITE) – who will present an overview of the Zero Waste Fashion Method
- Roberto Liberti (UCAMPANIA) – presenting an overview on their research on Cultural Fashion and Sustainable Heritage
- Joana Cunha (UMINHO) – explaining the foundation and achievements on Circular Fashion and Upcycling
- Ana Cristina Broega (UMINHO) – will act as a moderator, introducing the speakers, presenting the project's general mission and advancements, and promoting debates between partners and with the audience.

Textile Waste Management strategies (Portuguese)

Participants:

- Isabel Cantista – Dean of the School of Economics and Business Studies at University Lusíada, organizer of Global Fashion Conference 2023, who will present an overview of innovation and sustainability for Fashion Business
- Miguel A. Falcão – Textile Engineer specialized in sustainable fibers for textile Industry, debating on the importance, challenges, and opportunities of rPET, cotton and linen fiber generated with post-consumer waste.
- Dinis Marques – Sustainability specialist blending biological, ecological, and economic principles to address sustainability challenges.
- Ana Cristina Broega – moderator

Ucampania

The roundtables for the final project event will be held at UCampania's Officina Vanvitelli on July 3rd.

Introduction to the roundtables:

- Ornella Zerlenga – Director for the Architecture and Industrial Design at Ucampania
- Patrizia Ranzo – Research Director at Officina Vanvitelli

Roundtable participants:

UNICAMPANIA

Roberto Liberti – Lead Investigator at Fashion Alive Italy, will provide an overview of the structure and concept for Fashion Alive, the research and achievements of Ucampania on Cultural Heritage and Sustainable Fashion

Ornella Cirillo – Investigator at Fashion Alive Italy specialized in Fashion History and Cultural heritage, will present the cultural significance and starting point of the research on *corredo*.

Vincenzo Cirillo – Investigator at Fashion Alive Italy, will present the adaptation from research on *corredo* to sketching and prototyping to upcycle retrieved garments.

Chiara Scarpitti – Investigator at Fashion Alive Italy, will review the collection development and upcycling processes analysing the cultural and sociological impacts.

CREAMODITE

Gisela Fortuna, Lead Investigator of Creamodite, who will present an overview of the Zero Waste Fashion Method

UMINHO

Ana Cristina Broega, lead investigator of Uminho, will present Uminho's research and developments on Upcycling and Circular Fashion

Additionally, Ucampania will organize an **interdisciplinary exhibition** collecting all the partner's work:

Fashion History – Ornella Cirillo, Giulia Ceriani Sebregondi

Environment for Fashion – Lorenzo Capobianco, Concetta Tavoletta

Traditions and innovation in goldsmith design – Danila Jacazzi, Maria Dolores Morelli

Digital representation – Antonella Violano

Design Lab – Alessandra Avella, Vincenzo Cirillo

Fashion Design Lab – Caterina Fiorentino, Roberto Liberti, Simona Ottieri, Patrizia Ranzo, Maria Antonietta Sbordone, Chiara Scarpitti

Zero Waste Fashion Collection – selected items from the collection presented by Creamodite

Circular Fashion and Upcycling – selected items from the collection presented by Uminho